

EVALUATING IMPACTS OF IMAGING SPECTROMETER CALIBRATION ON MINERAL IDENTIFICATION AND MAPPING USING AIRBORNE DATA COLLECTIONS IN ALASKA, USA, AND KHANDAHAR, AFGHANISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Calibration of spectrometer data to reflectance is important to obtain accurate and robust results in identifying surface materials. Among the aspects that affect calibration are: sensor characterization, including channel wavelength position and bandpass, radiometric accuracy, and atmospheric correction. For the detection of surface minerals in soils and bedrock, inaccuracies in any of these aspects generally decrease the degree of mineral discriminations that can be made, for example, separating carbonates, serpentines, chlorites, and amphiboles. Because of their design, pushbroom spectrometers can have variable wavelength position and bandpass in the across-track direction. Well-calibrated airborne imaging spectrometer data collected using HyMap were used to examine the effects of inaccuracies in Hyperion wavelength position on mineral identifications and to explore empirical methods for calibrating data to reflectance. On steep terrains, at high latitudes, it is difficult to atmospherically correct imaging spectrometer data to surface reflectance. Using HyMap data collected in Wrangell-St. Elias National Park, Alaska, a simple atmospheric correction, assuming a single elevation and flat terrain, was compared to a complex atmospheric correction accounting for pixel-by-pixel variations in elevation and sensor viewing and illumination geometry.

Index Terms— hyperspectral, imaging spectroscopy, geology, soils, minerals, PRISM, MICA

1. DATA COLLECTION AND PROCESSING

1.1. Khandahar, Afghanistan

From August 22 to October 2, 2007, HyMap* [1] imaging spectrometer data were acquired over most of Afghanistan to support assessments of natural resources and hazards in Afghanistan by the U.S. Geological Survey. The 218 individual flight lines (see figure 1) composing the Afghanistan dataset, covering more than 438,000 square kilometers, were georeferenced to a mosaic of orthorectified Landsat images. The HyMap data were converted from

radiance to reflectance using a radiative transfer program in combination with ground-calibration sites and a network of cross-cutting calibration flight lines [2]. These data are the largest, contiguous coverage of terrestrial imaging spectrometer data collected to date, covering a surface area of more than 438,000 square kilometers. The coverage spans approximately 860 km east to west and 900 km north to south.

A Hyperion satellite image (scene id EO1H1540382007269110PU) that passed over the Khandahar, Afghanistan, ground calibration site on September 26, 2007, was processed to apparent surface reflectance using the ACORN (Atmospheric CORrection Now) version 6lx (ImSpec LLC, Palmdale, California, USA) radiative transfer program. Hyperion is a pushbroom imaging spectrometer with cross-track variation in its channel wavelength positions. A region of overlapping HyMap data was used to develop two empirical corrections for the Hyperion data: 1) a single set of correction factors for each channel developed from the overlap region and applied to all columns of the image, 2) column-by-column correction factors for each channel. The resulting two cross-calibrated reflectance data sets were analyzed for surface material cover. Because of the low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the Hyperion sensor, averaging of spectra was done for 3x3 and 5x5 pixel windows and the subsequent images were analyzed for surface material cover.

1.2. Wrangell-St. Elias National Park, Alaska, USA

In July, 2014, data were collected using the HyMap2 sensor [1] over the Nabesna Area of Interest (AOI) in the eastern Alaska Range (62 degrees N latitude). The HyMap2 imaging spectrometer measured reflected sunlight in 126 narrow channels spanning the 0.4 to 2.5 micron wavelength region of the electromagnetic spectrum. The data were collected at a nominal 6 m ground-instantaneous field of view (GIFOV). In July 2014 and July 2015, representative samples of geologic units were collected for ground verification of remote sensing data. During both field seasons, spectra of ground calibration sites and exposed rocks and soils were

collected using an ASD FieldSpec4 spectrometer (Panalytical, Boulder, Colorado, USA).

The HyMap2 data were converted from radiance to reflectance using a multistep calibration process [2]. First, the radiance data were converted to apparent surface reflectance using the radiative transfer correction programs ACORN and ATCOR-4 (ReSe Applications, Zurich, Switzerland). Subsequently, ground-based reflectance measurements from a calibration site were used to empirically correct residual atmospheric effects in both data sets. The two radiative transfer ground-calibrated (RTGC) data sets were analyzed for surface material cover.

2. MINERAL IDENTIFICATION AND MAPPING

Reflectance data from all spectrometers were processed using the Material Identification and Characterization Algorithm (MICA), a program written in Interactive Data Language (IDL; ExelisVIS, Boulder, Colorado, USA). MICA is a module of the USGS PRISM (Processing Routines in IDL for Spectroscopic Measurements) software [3]. The MICA analysis identifies the dominant mineral or mineral assemblage, with characteristic absorption features in the scanned wavelength range, in each pixel of imaging spectrometer data by comparing its reflectance spectrum to a reference spectral library of minerals, vegetation, water, and other materials.

3. RESULTS

Mineral maps derived from the column-by-column correction of Hyperion data show a greater resemblance to the reference HyMap mineral map than the single empirical correction (figure 2). Significant striping is apparent in the mineral identifications based on the single empirical correction (leftmost image in figure 2). Increasing pixel averaging further improves the mineral mapping for the column-by-column correction of Hyperion data (figure 3).

Mineral maps derived from the Alaska HyMap data reveal a greater degree of mineral discrimination was achieved using the more complex ATCOR-4 correction (figure 4). In the mineral map derived from the simple ACORN correction, most of the deposit is classified as montmorillonite clay. The ATCOR-4 shows a more intricate patterning of montmorillonite, muscovite, chlorite and gypsum, which is consistent with ground based single point field spectrometer measurements and imaging spectrometer results. Laboratory based analysis of hand samples confirm the mineral determinations in the ATCOR-4 result. Likely, the more subtle, secondary absorption features in muscovite, gypsum and chlorite are inadequately corrected in the ACORN result. Therefore, these minerals are not identified by the MICA analysis.

4. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. HyMap data collected in Afghanistan in 2007.

Figure 2. Surface material maps for Hyperion data with different cross-calibration methods compared to HyMap data.

Figure 3. Surface material maps for various levels of Hyperion pixel averaging compared to HyMap.

Figure 4. Surface mineral maps derived from two atmospheric correction procedures applied to HyMap data in Alaska.